

Seasonal Daylight Saving Time in UK: a long-standing, successful record with few reasons to alter

José María Martín-Olalla

*Universidad de Sevilla,
Facultad de Física,
Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada,
ES41012 Sevilla,
Spain**

Jorge Mira

*Universidade de Santiago de Compostela,
Facultade de Física,
Departamento de Física Aplicada and iMATUS,
ES15782 Santiago de Compostela,
Spain†*

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A letter response to the British Sleep Society position statement endorsing permanent winter time in UK. We review human activity in UK and the continued record of clocks regulations in this country since 1916.

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UK is an interesting case in the history of seasonal clocks (Daylight Saving Time) because it maintains a record of continued practice since its inception in 1916 —when British clocks were first set to UTC+01 (British summer time) during the summer season— except in the Second World War —when, in addition, clocks were advanced one more hour year round— and a brief excursion into permanent summer time in 1968-1971. British clocks have never been reset to UTC+00 (winter time or standard time) during the summer season since 1916, yet the British Sleep Society recently issued a position statement endorsing permanent winter time (Crawford *et al.*, 2024) in line with previous position statements issued

elsewhere. (Malow, 2022; Rishi *et al.*, 2024; Roenneberg *et al.*, 2019) We would like to raise here some key points that Crawford *et al.* (2024) do not mention and a context to clock regulations and human activity in UK. They are crucial to make a correct balance of the pros and cons of either choice related to the issue.

The seasonal clock regulations set two natural experiments. One of them has been thoroughly described by research papers in the past decades: the “immediate effects on sleep and circadian systems elicited by the abrupt switches” of one hour that the regulations set twice a year. These immediate effects are the downside of the practice and consist of a systematic, brief and slight increase of the risks in key issues like myocardial infarctions (Janszky and Ljung, 2008) and fatal traffic accidents (Fritz *et al.*, 2020) around transition dates. From an epidemiological point of view, these increases are weak, with z -scores likely below 0.5. (Martín-Olalla and Mira,

* olalla@us.es; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3750-9113>;
<https://ror.org/03yxnp24>

† jorge.mira@usc.es; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6024-6294>;
<https://ror.org/030eybx10>

2023)

The second natural experiment has been less addressed, and perhaps, less understood globally. It is the fact that clock regulations are an invitation to a bimodal human activity: early during the spring-summer and delayed during the autumn-winter. Note that this is not Crawford *et al.* (2024)'s "chronic effects of having schedules 1 hour earlier in relation to solar time for over half a year" because these "chronic effects", if they existed, cannot be separated "out from seasonal effects". Instead, the key issue to address in the second natural experiment is the human response to the external stimulus that clock regulations set after a long-standing continued practice.

Martín-Olalla (2019) studied microdata from the UK time use survey and analysed seasonal differences in human daily rhythms. The results show scarce, statistically insignificant seasonal differences. This refers to the timing (local time sleep/work onset, local time sleep/work offset) and to the daily totals (sleep time and working hours). Understandably, these observations are partially the result of people being comfortable with regular time schedules, say a working schedule from 09:00 to 17:00 throughout the year. But, with one hundred year of continued practice, these observations are also showing a lack of response against the regulations, and a commitment to the aims and goals of the practice: the alignment of work hours close to sunrise and greater use of outdoor recreation in the spring-summer evening. (Hudson, 1898; Willet, 1907) British citizens seem to have settled down to a late 09:00 to 17:00 (UTC+00) pre-set schedule during the autumn-winter season and an early 08:00 to 16:00 (UTC+00) pre-set schedule during the spring-summer season—which is rendered as 09:00 to 17:00 (UTC+01) nonetheless. They have not pushed for a delay of work hours during the summer, or for an advance of the work hours during the winter. In so doing they show a better alignment with the winter sunrise (morning light) than elsewhere in Europe where clock regulations were discontinued from 1945 to 1980. (Martín-Olalla, 2022) The lack of response is a telling response that challenges that the potential "chronic effects" can be attributed to the regulations. We note that early summer activity and late winter activity can be found elsewhere under more naturalistic conditions, (van Egmond *et al.*, 2019; Honma *et al.*, 1992; Martín-Olalla, 2020) for a thorough review see Martín-Olalla and Mira (2024).

Human physiology provides an explanation on this behaviour, therefore, an explanation on the physiological grounds of clock regulations, which indeed were described by their original sponsors. Crawford *et al.* (2024) (Section 2) note the importance of "timed light exposure" to keep circadian rhythms aligned to the solar day. At the 50° circle of latitude this is achieved in winter by delaying the onset of activity until the sun rises some 2 h later than the yearly average sunrise time and 2 h later than the sunrise time at the Equator. By the spring equinox,

the delay in sunrise times ceases to exist. Early morning light then "plays a central role in preventing our body clocks from becoming too late and aligning them adequately" with the day and pushes for an early activity. Modern, Extratropical societies synchronized by preset schedules can currently achieve this with the one-hour clock changing.

Why not a two-hour clock changing or two one-hour clock changing that would offset the two-hour delay that the winter sunrise set in UK? On the other side of the day "light exposure during the late evening delays sleep onset and our natural waking". Eventually the one-hour shift allows in UK—and elsewhere—a natural onset of the activity in winter—the most challenging season for the wake—and a natural onset of sleep in summer—the most challenging season for sleeping—. Figure 1 shows winter human activity (top) and summer human activity (bottom) in UK from the Harmonized European Time Use Survey (Eurostat, 2010) and highlights daylight (winter) and nighttime (summer). Notice that human activity resumes in winter (top panel) around the winter sunrise time SRW, while in summer (bottom panel), and under clock regulations, bedtimes still come after summer sunset time SSS.

Finally, we would like to put forward a few words on clocks to clarify some misunderstandings that often appear in this context. Not only winter time "aligns closely with the natural light-dark cycles of day and night"; summer time also does it. Both are set to one cycle per day, and just differ in a phase shift, which makes a difference for the preset time schedules that govern the rhythms of modern societies, but not for the natural light-dark cycles of day and night. Also, both winter time and summer time are standard times: they both apply to a wide area—UK in our present discussion—and are set to a whole number of hours relative to the prime meridian. Therefore opposing "standard time" to "daylight saving time" is misleading when it comes to analysing the aims and goals of the regulations, whereas opposing "winter time" to "summer time" catches the issues at stake.

Whether winter time or summer time be more practical or more adequate for a given purpose or on a given season is only a matter of preferences, uses or costumes. With one hundred years of continued practice and the overwhelming majority of UK population having lived only under this alternating setting, winter time is *de facto* the standard of time in winter, and sets the standard preset schedules during the winter in accordance with the winter light and dark conditions. Likewise, summer time is *de facto* the standard of time in summer, and sets the standard summer preset schedules in accordance with the light and dark conditions in summer. We note that UK tested once permanent summer time (1968-1971) with no success due to the discomfort that onset times ahead of SRW brought. On the contrary, since 1916 permanent winter time has not even been tested or considered seri-

Figure 1 The yearly averaged wake (not sleeping and not doing personal care) participation rate and the yearly averaged work participation rate in United Kingdom as obtained from the Harmonised European Time Use Survey (Hetus), black thick lines. The thin grey lines show the alternate scenario where permanent summer time (top) or permanent winter time (bottom) would apply. The top panel annotates the winter sunrise (SRW) and the winter sunset (SSW), daytime is highlighted in yellow shade. The bottom panel annotates the summer sunrise (SRS) and the summer sunset (SSS), with nighttime highlighted in grey shade. SRW^- is one hour ahead SRW. The horizontal axes display local time. Note from top to bottom the horizontal axes are synchronous: the change in time zone is offset by a shift in the horizontal scale. In winter (top) sleep onset, and work onset occur around SRW. Correspondingly, bedtimes come around sunset in summer (bottom). For simplicity, solar time marks are set for $52.1^\circ N, 1.4^\circ W$.

ously. Back in 1916, and seemingly once and for all, a regular summer schedule from 08:00 to 16:00 (UTC+00) was preferred to a regular summer schedule from 09:00 to 17:00 (UTC+00). Currently, this preference is still shown by polls (Rubin, 2023), when scores for permanent summer time regularly outnumber scores for permanent winter time. It is like saying: “we love our current summer schedule, please do not delay it.”

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

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REFERENCES

- Crawford, Megan R, Eva C. Winnebeck, Malcolm von Schantz, Maria Gardani, Michelle A. Miller, Victoria Revell, Alanna Hare, Caroline L. Horton, Simon Durrant, and Joerg Steier (2024), “The british sleep society position statement on daylight saving time in the uk,” *Journal of Sleep Research* **34**, e14352.
- van Egmond, Lieve, Martin Ekman, and Christian Benedict (2019), “Bed and rise times during the age of enlightenment: A case report,” *Journal of Sleep Research* **28**, e12862.
- Eurostat, (2010), “Harmonised european time use surveys (hetus). rounds 1 and 2,” .
- Fritz, Josef, Trang VoPham, Kenneth P. Wright, and Céline Vetter (2020), “A chronobiological evaluation of the acute effects of daylight saving time on traffic accident risk,” *Current Biology* **30**, 729–735.
- Honma, K I, S. Honma, M. Kohsaka, and N. Fukuda (1992), “Seasonal variation in the human circadian rhythm: Dissociation between sleep and temperature rhythm,” *American Journal of Physiology - Regulatory Integrative and Comparative Physiology* **262**, R885–R891.
- Hudson, George Vernon (1898), “On seasonal time,” *Transactions and Proceedings of the New Zealand Royal Society* **31**, 577–598.
- Janszky, Imre, and Rickard Ljung (2008), “Shifts to and from daylight saving time and incidence of myocardial infarction,” *New England Journal of Medicine* **359**, 1966–1968.
- Malow, Beth A (2022), “It is time to abolish the clock change and adopt permanent standard time in the united states: a sleep research society position statement,” *Sleep* **45**, zsac236.
- Martín-Olalla, José María (2019), “The long term impact of daylight saving time regulations in daily life at several circles of latitude,” *Scientific Reports* **9**, 18466.
- Martín-Olalla, José María (2020), “Scandinavian bed and rise times in the age of enlightenment and in the 21st century show similarity, helped by daylight saving time,” *Journal of Sleep Research* **29**, e12916.
- Martín-Olalla, José María (2022), “A chronobiological evaluation of the risks of canceling daylight saving time,” *Chronobiology International* **39**, 1–4.
- Martín-Olalla, José María, and Jorge Mira (2023), “Sample size bias in the empirical assessment of the acute risks associated with daylight saving time transitions,” *Chronobiology International* **40**, 186–191.
- Martín-Olalla, José María, and Jorge Mira (2024), “Assessing the best hour to start the day: an appraisal of seasonal daylight saving time,” [zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.13990240](https://zenodo.org/record/105281/zenodo.13990240).
- Rishi, Muhammad Adeel, Jocelyn Y Cheng, Abigail R Strang, Kathy Sexton-Radek, Gautam Ganguly, Amy Licis, Erin E Flynn-Evans, Michael W Berneking, Raj Bhui, Jennifer Creamer, ; Vaishnavi Kundel, Andrew R Spector, Olatunji Olaoye, Sarah D Hashmi, Fariha ; Abbasi-Feinberg, Alexandre Rocha Abreu, Indira Gurubhagavattula, Vishesh K Kapur, David Kuhlmann, Jennifer Martin, Eric Olson, Susheel Patil, James Rowley, Anita Shelgikar, Lynn Marie Trotti, Emerson M Wickwire, and Shannon S Sullivan (2024), “Permanent standard time is the optimal choice for health and safety: an american academy of sleep medicine position statement,” *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine* **20**, 121–125.
- Roenneberg, Till, Anna Wirz-Justice, Debra J. Skene, Sonia Ancoli-Israel, Kenneth P. Wright, Derk-Jan Dijk, Phyllis Zee, Michael R. Gorman, Eva C. Winnebeck, and Elizabeth B. Klerman (2019), “Why should we abolish daylight saving time?” *Journal of Biological Rhythms* **34**, 227–230.
- Rubin, Rita (2023), “Groundswell grows for permanent daylight saving time, but medical societies overwhelmingly support year-round standard time,” *JAMA* 10.1001/JAMA.2023.0159.
- Willet, William (1907), *The waste of daylight*.

MANUSCRIPT TIME LINE

On Saturday 2 November 2024 Xavier Lombardero informed JM about a news release posted on [Eurekalert](https://www.eurekalert.org/news-releases/1062135) <https://www.eurekalert.org/news-releases/1062135> announcing Crawford *et al.* (2024). JM touched JMM-O and both agreed on writing a response Letter to the Editor.

The manuscript was outlined and written during the next weekend. On Sunday 10 November 2024 the manuscript was submitted to *JSR* at 09:20pm CET. The manuscript was returned to the authors on the next day at 02:30pm CET, due to slight mishap in the source files. It was quickly resubmitted at 03:30pm CET that day. On Tuesday 12 November 2024 at 11:00am the manuscript went to the Editor who accepted at 02:30pm CET. It was published online on Friday 29 November 2024.